

EDIBLE LANDSCAPES: THE ECONOMIC AND ECOLOGICAL BOUNTY

Nibir Pratim Choudhury, Prerna Deka

1. PhD Scholar, Department of Business Administration,
University of Science & Technology Meghalaya2. Assistant Project Scientist, APART, Assam Agricultural University
Horticulture Research Station, Kahikuchi

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Abstract

Edible landscaping, a mix of beauty and bounty, is emerging as a game changer in sustainable living. This novel practice, which combines aesthetics and practicality, reimagines our landscapes as dynamic, productive areas. Beyond the appeal of exquisite gardens, edible landscaping has economic potential—it promotes local entrepreneurship, creates jobs, and diversifies income streams. Its environmental benefit is as compelling, as it promotes biodiversity, water conservation, and soil health, which are all permaculture concepts. Socially, it promotes participation in the community, education, and well-being, strengthening the structural integrity of our neighbourhoods.

The present research explains the ideas and techniques of edible landscaping, investigates its economic potential, and reveals its deep environmental and social consequences. The recommendations for smooth integration emphasise the importance of supportive legislation, community participation, and education. Edible landscaping is more than simply a visual feast; it's a formula for resilience, a greener future, and sustainability in which our landscapes not only look good but also benefit our communities and the environment.

Keywords: Edible, landscape, innovation, sustainable, entrepreneurship, biodiversity.

Introduction

Landscapes and food are important and necessary subjects (Zeunert & Waterman, 2018). The edible landscape is a relatively new multifunctional landscaping approach. As a landscape made up of plant species that humans can eat, it emphasises the purpose and value of the landscape and is distinguished by edibility, economy, and ornamentation (Zheng, 2010). Landscape architecture and urban planning began to trend towards modern pastoral cities in the nineteenth century (Cui, 2010). In the context of the struggle between urban landscape building and agricultural cultivation, the edible landscape considers both functions and addresses the need for cooperation between healthy and environmentally friendly urban agriculture and habitation.

However, certain edible sceneries are acceptable. For instance, the food safety of certain edible landscapes placed near roadways may be questioned. The rational growth of edible landscapes must adhere to the following principles. First, it must adhere to the principles of sustainability and organic cultivation. The fundamental concept of an edible landscape is to ensure it is sustainable and ecologically sound, with planning and planting based on environmental protection principles. To maintain food safety, edible landscapes on the premises should be grown organically. Second, edible landscapes' diverse purposes and values should be completely developed, with multifunctional synergies realised in regards to ornamental and practical usage, and also popular education and research (Lin, et al., 2022).

Edible landscaping has been increasingly popular in recent years as towns and individuals seek long-term solutions to environmental problems, food security challenges, and economic difficulties (Zheng & Chou, 2023). Traditional landscaping frequently prioritises aesthetics above practicality, employing decorative plants that may provide little practical benefit beyond their visual appeal (Brook, 2018). Edible landscaping, on the contrary, is the deliberate cultivation of plants that have both aesthetic and edible properties, transforming places into productive and sustainable ecosystems (Rupprecht et al., 2023).

Increasing global population and urbanisation have increased the demand for food, putting a strain on traditional methods of farming and land resources (Satterthwaite, McGranahan, & Tacoli, 2010). Simultaneously, the negative consequences of climate change, including extreme weather and dwindling biodiversity, highlight the importance of innovative and sustainable approaches to agricultural production and environmental protection.

Edible plant integration into landscaping designs is based on permaculture, sustainable agriculture, and agroecology ideas. These concepts emphasise the need to work with nature rather than against it, so boosting biodiversity, water conservation, and soil health (Yadav et al., 2023). Edible landscaping adheres to these ideals

by blending the beauty of ornamental vegetation with the practicality of food-producing ones, resulting in landscapes that are both visually appealing and environmentally sustainable.

As the globe grapples with 21st-century challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and economic inequality, there is a growing realisation of their interdependence. Edible landscaping evolves as a comprehensive solution that solves numerous difficulties at once. It can boost local economies by providing new job possibilities, improving food security by encouraging local food production, and developing community resilience through communal spaces and collaborative activities (Karaca, 2019).

This research paper will look at the ideas and methods of edible landscaping, as well as its economic potential for generating livelihoods and appraising its social and environmental effects. Understanding the various benefits of edible landscaping allows communities, individuals, and policymakers to make informed decisions about incorporating this sustainable practice into overall development efforts. Finally, the examination of edible landscaping as an appropriate strategy reflects an overall trend towards sustainable as well as regenerative techniques that benefit both people and the environment.

Principles and Practices of Edible Landscaping

Edible landscaping blends the visual attractiveness of traditional landscaping with the practical advantages of growing edible plants. Edible landscaping combines permaculture, sustainable agriculture, and agroecology concepts to create mutually beneficial, productive areas that benefit the environment and community well-being.

1. *Biodiversity and Plant Selection* (FAO 2010)
 - i. Native and Climate-Appropriate Plants: Consumption of native & climate-appropriate edible plants to promote resilience and reduce water, pesticide, and fertiliser usage.
 - ii. Polyculture: Plant a varied range of food species to promote biodiversity by supporting growth, resistance to insects, and nutrient cycling.
2. *Water conservation* (Zhang et al., 2021).
 - i. Use water-efficient practices like drip irrigation and mulching to conserve water and keep soil moist.
 - ii. Implement rainwater harvesting systems to gather and use rainfall for irrigation, reducing reliance on traditional water sources.
3. *Soil Health and Fertility* (Reddy, 2017):
 - i. Companion Planting: Use companion planting to improve soil fertility, repel pests, and promote beneficial interactions between plants.
 - ii. Organic Practices: Instead of using synthetic fertilisers and pesticides, prioritise soil health, nutrient cycling, and microbial diversity.

4. *Design considerations* (Croft 2023):
 - i. Functional Layout: Incorporate edible plants into the landscape to maximise productivity while maintaining beauty.
 - ii. Vertical planting: Use vertical planting techniques to maximise space while developing visually pleasing designs.
 - iii. Edible Hedges and Borders: Replace ornamental hedges & borders with edible substitutes to improve landscape functioning.
5. *Community Engagement* (Ben-Othmen et al., 2023).
 - i. Community Gardens: Establish community gardens to encourage teamwork in cultivating and maintaining edible landscapes.
 - ii. Educational Programmes: Organise workshops to promote edible landscaping and encourage community engagement.
6. *Permaculture ethics* (Ward, 2015):
 - i. Earth Care: Prioritise sustainable land utilisation practices that benefit the environment, biodiversity, and ecosystem health.
 - ii. People Care: Ensure edible landscaping initiatives prioritise community well-being and inclusivity, creating accessible and beneficial environments for all.
 - iii. Fair Share: Ensure equal allocation of resources and benefits, including sharing surplus production within the community.
7. *Maintenance and Harvest*:
 - i. Regular Pruning: Regular pruning improves plant health and productivity, resulting in optimal yields.
 - ii. Harvest Planning: Create a systematic harvest plan to maximise productivity and maintain a consistent supply of fresh produce.
8. *Integration with Urban Planning* (Ochoa, Jiménez, & Olmo, 2020):
 - i. Zoning Policies: Promote "zoning policies" which encourage edible planting in urban and suburban regions.
 - ii. Green Infrastructure: Including edible landscapes in green infrastructure efforts improves urban resilience and wellness.

Methodology

This study adopts a secondary data methodology, drawing on previously published literature, research papers, and studies on edible landscaping. To acquire information on edible landscaping principles, economic potential, and social and environmental implications, extensive searches were undertaken in academic databases, scientific journals, and reliable sources. The analysis entails combining findings from several sources to provide a thorough summary. The secondary data methodology allows for a complete evaluation of existing knowledge, revealing insights into the numerous aspects of edible landscaping and supporting evidence-based conclusions.

Discussions

Vegetables used in edible landscaping

A variety of plants is essential for an attractive vegetable garden. The same landscaping design principles should be followed while establishing a garden, whether attractive plants or vegetable species are used. Any plant, either a flower, a dendrological species, or a vegetable, can be ornamental if placed in the appropriate location. Depending on the type of landscape design and the pedo-climatic conditions, varieties of vegetables can be chosen to meet the requirements. Vegetable species, like decorative species, are embellished with designs, leaves, flowers, and colour. One disadvantage is that there are fewer vegetables available. But now there are ornamental forms for all of the major vegetable categories. Beautiful gardens can be made utilising traditional vegetable species; the trick is to position them in the right area with flower species (Almusaed, 2018).

1. *Root Vegetables*: Root vegetables such as carrots, parsley, red beets, celery, and radish are suitable for landscaping. These

have an abundant leaf structure, making them ideal for creating vegetative carpets. Carrots, like ferns, have rosette-shaped leaves and can be utilised to construct vegetative beds to separate batches. Parsley with curly leaves can be used for a pleasing aesthetic effect. The red beetroot is another attractive vegetable in this group that adds colour to any space with its leaves. Bull's Blood is the most decorative kind of red beetroot, with dark crimson leaves.

2. *Cruciferous*: The cabbage group is the following group of vegetables, and it stands out for its design and colour palette. Flowering kale variants can be light-coloured, with one colour (green, white, blue, red, pink, or purple), or with two colours (green with white, green with pink, dark red with pink, or green with red. Spivony ornamental cabbage has miniature heads measuring 7-8 cm in diameter, and corrugated leaves making it suitable for ornamental use. Leaves of young red cabbage are light blue or grey, with dark red veins. When they grow, they turn dark blue, then scarlet, with a grey gloss. Cabbage remains the most visually appealing vegetable, whether grown for its head or leaves. This vegetable may successfully ensure winter décor due to its low-temperature tolerance, and the colours become more intense, gorgeous, and decorative when frosts fall.
3. *Leafy Greens*: Leeks and green onions constitute two of the most visually appealing bulbs. Thin leaves on bulbs allow designers to contrast them with other leaf shapes. Another advantage is that they are compact and grow steadily. The nicest element is their blooming season, when they produce a large number of flowery stems in a variety of colours and their aesthetic is at its peak. However, the flowering time is brief, ranging from three weeks to one month. Petiole beetroot, chicory, fennel, and lettuce are examples of green vegetables that are particularly ornamental. They embellish with their forms and colours, allowing us to create amazing chromatic games.
4. *Solanaceae Vegetables*: The Solanaceae family includes the tomato and pepper. The pepper plant adorns its appearance with dark green, velvety foliage and fruit. The fruit is painted with a range of colours, which include white, red, yellow, and purple. It is additionally embellished with its shape. Tomatoes are also visually appealing because of their leaves, different fruit colours, and different fruit shapes.
5. *Legumes and Capsules*: The ornamental aspects of the vegetables raised for their pods, beans, and capsules are not very noteworthy, but since they are climbers, with flexible stalks, they are appealing if supported. When the flowers blossom, they are brightly coloured.
6. *Cucurbits*: Cucurbits are another highly attractive vegetable group. Fruit is the most prominent decorative component of this group. They have a variety of intriguing and beautiful colours and shapes.

Economic Potential of Edible Landscaping

Edible landscaping is a viable economic development strategy, providing opportunities for individuals, neighbourhoods, and local economies. By deliberately introducing edible plants into conventional landscapes, this strategy not only promotes environmental sustainability as well as offers a variety of economic benefits.

1. Income Generation:

- i. Local Entrepreneurship: Edible landscaping provides chances for local entrepreneurs to start enterprises focused on the cultivation, management, and sale of edible plants. This encompasses the provision of landscaping services, plant nurseries, and retailing of fresh fruit.
- ii. Value-Added Products: Entrepreneurs can increase the value of edible plants by processing them into products including

saucers, jams, jellies, and herbal tea. This diversification improves revenue sources and market potential.

2. *Employment Opportunities:*
 - i. Landscaping and Maintenance: The development and maintenance of edible landscapes necessitate specialised personnel, creating job possibilities in horticulture, landscaping, and maintenance.
 - ii. Local Agriculture Jobs: As edible landscaping encourages local production of food, there is a greater demand for agricultural labourers, which contributes to job creation.
3. *Small-Scale Farming and Urban Agriculture:*
 - i. Community Gardens: Edible landscaping frequently includes the establishment of communal gardens, which give people access to land for cultivation. This cooperative approach promotes urban agriculture and allows people to cultivate their own food.
 - ii. Micro-Farming: Small-scale farmers can make use of limited areas by implementing edible landscaping strategies, allowing them to diversify their agricultural produce and income streams.
4. *Tourism and Cultural Events:*
 - i. Tourism Attractions: Well-constructed edible landscapes may function as tourist attractions, attracting tourists who want to learn about sustainable techniques and local agriculture.
 - ii. Cultural Events: Farmers' markets, workshops, and food festivals organised within edible landscapes help to boost the local economy by attracting people and producing cash.
5. *Diversification of Income Sources:*
 - i. Risk Mitigation: Edible landscaping enables individuals and neighbourhoods to diversify their revenue sources, lowering exposure to economic swings and increasing overall financial resilience.
 - ii. Seasonal Harvests: The sequenced harvesting of diverse food plants throughout the year generates a consistent income stream, which helps to alleviate the seasonal character of traditional agriculture.
6. *Local Market Development:*
 - i. Fresh Produce Markets: Edible landscaping helps to grow local markets for fresh produce, allowing farmers and local entrepreneurs to sell directly to the customers.
 - ii. Community-Supported Agriculture (CSA): Initiatives such as CSA programmes, in which consumers subscribe to get frequent deliveries of locally farmed produce, improve the relationship between farmers and customers, supporting a thriving local economy.
7. *Educational Programs and Workshops:*
 - i. Training and Workshops: Educational programmes on sustainable agriculture and edible landscaping can be marketed, allowing trainers and professionals to earn money.
 - ii. Consulting Services: Individuals, communities, and corporations interested in developing edible landscaping projects might benefit from consulting services provided by industry experts.
8. *Municipal Revenue Generation:*
 - i. Permitting and Licensing: Municipalities can make cash by implementing permitting and licencing systems for edible landscaping projects, guaranteeing zoning compliance, and encouraging responsible practices.
 - ii. Increased Property Values: Well-kept edible landscapes raise property values, which contributes to higher municipal tax revenue.

Environmental Impacts of Edible Landscaping

Edible landscaping has a significant impact on the environment and the community's social fabric because it combines aesthetic appeal with practical productivity. Understanding these consequences is

critical for encouraging sustainable practices and instilling a sense of collective responsibility.

1. *Biodiversity Conservation:*
 - i. Enhanced Habitat Diversity: Edible landscaping, which involves the growing of a variety of plants, helps to promote habitat diversity by sustaining a variety of birds, insects, and beneficial microbes.
 - ii. Preservation of Native Species: The deliberate introduction of native and climate-appropriate vegetation helps preserve the local biodiversity by supporting the establishment of species suitable to the specific ecological situations of the location.
2. *Soil Health and Conservation:*
 - i. Improved Soil Structure: Mulching and organic cultivation are two edible landscaping strategies that improve soil structure by increasing nutrient availability, water retention, and microbial variety.
 - ii. Reduced Soil Erosion: Establishing ground cover with edible plants reduces soil erosion, protects against the depletion of fertile topsoil, and improves overall soil health.
3. *Water Conservation:*
 - i. Efficient Water Use: Drip irrigation methods, rainfall collecting, and water-efficient plant selections in edible landscaping all help to reduce water consumption when compared to traditional landscaping practices.
 - ii. Mitigation of Urban Heat Island Effect: Green spaces developed through edible landscaping help to reduce the heat island effect, lowering the surrounding temperature and reducing the need for water-intensive cooling methods.
4. *Chemical-Free Practices:*
 - i. Elimination of Synthetic Pesticides and Fertilizers: Edible landscaping frequently uses organic approaches, which eliminate or considerably reduce the application of synthetic pesticides and fertilisers. This helps to reduce soil contamination and water pollution.
5. *Carbon Sequestration:*
 - i. Carbon-Positive Practices: Edible landscapes, particularly those featuring perennial plants, support carbon sequestration, which helps to minimise the effects of climate change by trapping and depositing atmospheric carbon dioxide.

Social Impacts

1. *Community Engagement:*
 - i. Strengthened Social Bonds: Edible landscaping initiatives, particularly community gardens, generate shared areas that enhance social relationships, foster a sense of belonging, and promote environmental stewardship.
 - ii. Inclusive Participation: The inclusive character of edible landscaping invites individuals of all ages, experiences and abilities to take part, thus increasing social cohesiveness.
2. *Education and Awareness:*
 - i. Hands-On Learning: Edible landscaping educational programmes offer hands-on learning experiences while also raising awareness of sustainable agriculture methods and local production of food.
 - ii. Empowerment through Knowledge: Increased understanding enables people to make more educated decisions about the sources of their food, fostering a feeling of empowerment and self-reliance.
3. *Health and Well-being:*
 - i. Access to Fresh Produce: Edible landscaping encourages access to fresh, locally produced food, which helps to enhance nutrition and general health in communities.
 - ii. Physical and Mental Well-being: Gardening activities have been linked to physical exercise and favourable mental health results, which improves the well-being of those active in edible landscaping.

4. *Urban Aesthetics and Liveability:*

- i. Enhanced Aesthetics: Edible landscaping improves the aesthetics of cities as well as suburbs, making them more appealing and vibrant places to live.
- ii. Increased Liveability: Well-designed edible landscapes generate enticing public places that improve the overall living standards of communities by encouraging outdoor activities and socialising.

5. *Food Security and Resilience:*

- i. Local Food Production: Edible landscaping promotes local food production, reduces reliance on long-distance supply chains, and improves food security.
- ii. Community Resilience: Edible landscaping improves community resilience by encouraging self and local resilience in the face of external shocks such as economic uncertainty and food supply chain disruption.

Recommendations for the Integration of Edible Landscaping

As edible landscaping develops in popularity, it is critical to provide direction for its successful incorporation into varied environments. The ideas below are intended to help with the successful inclusion of edible landscaping into rural, urban, and suburban settings, while also assuring sustainable practices that maximise environmental, social, and economic advantages.

1. *Develop and Implement Supportive Policies:*

- i. Zoning Regulations: Municipalities should explore revising zoning restrictions to accept and promote edible landscaping, enabling the seamless integration of plants that produce food into traditional landscape design.
- ii. Incentives: Provide incentives, such as tax rebates or grants, to property owners and businesses that implement edible landscaping principles, thereby encouraging widespread adoption.

2. *Establish Community Gardens and Green Spaces:*

- i. Community Collaboration: Encourage the development of community gardens, allotted sites, and public green spaces to promote community engagement and shared responsibility for edible landscape maintenance.
- ii. Accessibility: Design these areas such that they are accessible to all members of the community, including those with restricted mobility, ensuring inclusion.

3. *Implement Educational Programs:*

- i. School Initiatives: Incorporate edible landscaping school educational programmes to teach the next generation about sustainable agriculture techniques and instil a feeling of environmental responsibility.
- ii. Community Workshops: Organise workshops and training programmes for local businesses, community members, and landscapers to raise awareness of the ideas and advantages of edible landscaping.

4. *Collaborate with Local Businesses:*

- i. Restaurant Partnerships: Encourage collaboration between edible landscapers and local restaurants to establish a local supply chain that will allow businesses to source fresh produce directly from neighbouring edible landscapes.
- ii. Economic Development Initiatives: Collaborate with the nearby chambers of commerce to emphasise the economic advantages of edible landscaping, positioning it as a realistic and appealing choice for businesses and entrepreneurs.

5. *Support Research and Development:*

- i. Demonstration Projects: Contribute to demonstration projects that highlight successful edible landscape implementations and serve as practical models for businesses, communities, and governments.
- ii. Research Initiatives: Support research on plant varieties that can thrive in different soil types, climates, and spaces in order to improve the effectiveness and durability of edible landscapes.

6. *Encourage Green Infrastructure Integration:*

- i. Urban Planning: Incorporate edible landscaping in urban planning plans, including green infrastructure efforts, to improve sustainability and resilience.
- ii. Corporate Campus Design: Promote institutions and businesses to use edible landscaping in their campus designs to foster an affinity with the environment and sustainable practices.

7. *Foster Collaboration Between Stakeholders:*

- i. Multi-Sectoral Partnerships: Encourage collaboration among local governments, environmental organisations, community groups, and companies to establish a supportive and coordinated network for edible landscaping programmes.
- ii. Public-Private Partnerships: Investigate public-private partnerships to support and implement massive edible landscaping projects, combining the distinctive qualities of both sectors.

8. *Prioritize Environmental and Social Equity:*

- i. Equitable Access: Ensure that edible landscaping helps every member of the community, regardless of socioeconomic class or background.
- ii. Community Consultation: Involve local people in edible landscaping decision-making processes, taking into account cultural customs and preferences.

9. *Monitor and Evaluate Impact:*

- i. Data Collection: Create methods for gathering data on the social, environmental, and economic implications of edible landscaping projects to guide future initiatives and advancements.
- ii. Performance Metrics: Create performance criteria to monitor the success and efficacy of edible landscaping, such as economic development, biodiversity enhancement, and community participation.

Conclusion

Edible landscaping offers a compelling and long-term solution to today's difficulties. It brings aesthetics and practicality together smoothly, providing a harmonic approach to rural, urban, and suburban surroundings. The economic potential of edible landscaping, from local businesses to job prospects, helps to build resilient and dynamic economies. Environmentally, it is a champion of soil health, biodiversity, and water conservation, exemplifying sustainability and climate resilience. Socially, it promotes education, community engagement, and increased well-being by building environments that encourage shared responsibility and inclusivity.

Proactive steps are necessary to fully realise the transforming potential of edible landscaping, such as encouraging legislation, cooperative neighbourhood projects, and educational campaigns. Ensuring social and environmental fairness takes precedence so that everyone can benefit from it. Edible landscaping becomes a beacon for humanity to work towards a sustainable future—a real example of how people can live in harmony with the natural world while promoting biodiversity, aesthetic appeal, and economic vibrancy. Adopting edible landscaping is a concrete step towards a more resilient, greener world where landscapes function as vibrant ecosystems that support and enhance the communities in addition to being aesthetically pleasing.

Reference

1. **Almusaed, A. (2018).** *Landscape Architecture - The Sense of Places, Models and Applications*. London: InTech.
2. **Ben-Othmen, M. A., Cardoze, V., Hani, J., & Sauvee, L. (2023).** Community-based urban agriculture for food justice: a review. In *Urban and Regional Agriculture* (pp. 11-40). Academic Press.
3. **Brook, I. (2018).** *Aesthetic appreciation of landscape*. London: Routledge.

4. **Croft, E. (2023).** *Designing an Edible Landscape: The Perfect Blend of Functionality and Aesthetics*. Retrieved December 2023, from Frisella Nursery: <https://frisellannursery.com/designing-an-edible-landscape-the-perfect-blend-of-functionality-and-aesthetics/>
5. **Cui, C. (2010).** *Supplying the City*. Tianjin, China: Tianjin University.
6. **FAO. (2010, April).** *Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture*. Retrieved December 2023, from Food and Agriculture Organization: https://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/biodiversity_paia/PAR-FAO-book_lr.pdf
7. **Karaca, E. (2019).** Edible Landscapes as a Solution to Food Security Problem. In *Theory and Practice in Social Sciences* (pp. 227-240). Sofia, Bulgaria: St. Kliment Ohridski University Press.
8. **Larkcom, J. (2002).** *Grow Your Own Vegetables*. London: Frances Lincoln Publishers Ltd.
9. **Lin, J., Zhou, M., Luo, H., Zhang, B., Feng, J., & Yi, Q. (2022).** Analysis of the Emotional Identification Mechanism of Campus Edible Landscape from the Perspective of Emotional Geography: An Empirical Study of a Chinese University Town. *International Journal of Environment Research and Public Health*, 19(18), 11425.
10. **Muluneh, M. G. (2021).** Impact of climate change on biodiversity and food security: a global perspective—a review article. *Agriculture & Food Security*, 10(36).
11. **Ochoa, C. Y., Jiménez, D. F., & Olmo, R. M. (2020).** Green Infrastructure Planning in Metropolitan Regions to Improve the Connectivity of Agricultural Landscapes and Food Security. *Land*, 9(414), 1-23.
12. **Reddy, P. P. (2017).** Companion Planting. In *Agro-ecological Approaches to Pest Management for Sustainable Agriculture* (pp. 149-164). Singapore: Springer.
13. **Rupprecht, C., Gartner, N., Cui, L., Sardeshpande, M., McGreevy, S. R., & Spiegelberg, M. (2023).** *Defining edible landscapes: a multilingual systematic review*. Retrieved December 2023, from SocArXiv: <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/64uvj>
14. **Satterthwaite, D., McGranahan, G., & Tacoli, C. (2010).** Urbanization and its implications for food and farming. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, 365, 2809-2820.
15. **Ward, B. (2015).** *Permaculture In Development: An introduction to permaculture and its application in agriculture development*. Retrieved December 2023, from Echo Community: <https://www.echocommunity.org/en/resources/7dae3899-6abb-483b-8ad6-67dd201654b5>
16. **Yadav, S. P., Lahutiya, V., Ghimire, N. P., Yadav, B., & Paudel, P. (2023).** Exploring innovation for sustainable agriculture: A systematic case study of permaculture in Nepal. *Heliyon*, 9(5).
17. **Zeunert, J., & Waterman, T. (2018).** *Routledge Handbook of Landscape and Food*. London: Routledge.
18. **Zhang, W., Sheng, J., Li, Z., Weindorf, D. C., Hu, G., Xuan, J., & Zhao, H. (2021).** Integrating rainwater harvesting and drip irrigation for water use efficiency improvements in apple orchards of northwest China. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 275, 109728.
19. **Zheng, W. J. (2010).** *Survey and Planning of Edible Landscapes in Residential Areas in Chengdu*. Yaan, China: Sichuan Agricultural University.
20. **Zheng, Z.-W., & Chou, R.-J. (2023).** Promoting the Development of Edible Landscapes in Suburban Areas with Place Branding—A Case Study in Taiwan. *Land*, 12(6), 1237.